

THE INFLUENCE OF SUBSTITUTION ON THE FORMATION
OF DERIVATIVES OF α -HYDRINDONE AND α -TETRALONE.
SYNTHESIS OF 1:2:3:4-TETRAHYDRO-
NAPHTHALENE-1:2-DICARBOXYLIC ACID.

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The present investigation describes a method for the synthesis of 1:2-dicarboxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalenes, which are important for the synthesis of benzanthracene derivatives with carcinogenic property.

Benzaldehyde cyanohydrin is allowed to react with the sodium salt of ethyl cyanoacetate and the sodium derivative of ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- β -phenylpropionate (I, R=R'=H) is allowed to react when with ethyl chloroacetate diethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- α -phenyl-*n*-propane- β -dicarboxylate (I, R'=H; R=CH₂CO₂Et) is obtained. On hydrolysis with sulphuric acid (70%) the latter yields α -phenyl-*n*-propane- $\alpha\beta\gamma$ -tricarboxylic acid, m.p. 204° (II, R=H). The acid (II, R=H), described by Hetcht (*Monatsh*, 1903, **24**, 371) melts at 110-115°, then solidifies and finally melts again at 196-201° and it is identical with α -phenyl-tricarballic acid, m.p. 199°, obtained by Stobbe and Fischer (*Annalen*, 1901, **315**, 231, 245). Uncertain melting point is often characteristic of tribasic acids and is doubtless due to the formation of a small amount of anhydride. The acid (II, R=H) in presence of sulphuric acid undergoes ring-closure to yield the keto-acid (III, R=CO). It is, however, possible that the product, instead of being tetrahydronaphthalene derivative might be the hydrindone derivative (IV). On Clemmensen reduction it yields a gummy acid from which 1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-1:2-dicarboxylic acid (III, R=CH₂) crystallises out on keeping in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid for a long time. The gummy acid might be a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-tetrahydronaphthalenes or a mixture of naphthalene and hydrindone derivative.

α -(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-*n*-propane- $\alpha\beta\gamma$ -tricarboxylic acid (II, R=OMe) obtained by hydrolysing diethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- α -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-propane- $\beta\gamma$ -dicarboxylate (I, R'=OMe; R=CH₂CO₂Et) on the other hand, under similar treatment does not cyclise but is sulphonated.

It has been shown by Thorpe and others (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 2185) that phenylsuccinic acid undergoes ring-closure to yield 1-ketohydrindene-3-carboxylic acid. An extension of the method for the synthesis of

methoxy derivative of hydrindones has been abandoned as it is found that the ring-closure of *p*-methoxyphenylsuccinic acid or its ester does not take place with phosphorus pentoxide or with sulphuric acid.

p-Methoxyphenylsuccinic acid (*cf.* Baker and Lapworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 560; Chrzaszewska, *Roczniki Chem.*, 1925, 5, 1, 33; Carson and Stoughton, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2825) has been prepared by hydrolysing ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-propionate (I, R' = OMe; R = H) with 20% sulphuric acid.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

EXPERIMENTAL.

*Diethyl $\alpha\beta$ -Dicyano- α -phenyl-*n*-propane- $\beta\gamma$ -dicarboxylate* (I, R' = H; R = CH₂·CO₂Et).—Mandelic nitrile (66 g.) was added in small quantities at a time to an alcoholic suspension of sodio-cyanoacetate, prepared from ethyl cyanoacetate (56 g.), alcohol (140 c.c.) and sodium (11.6 g.). The temperature was regulated by cooling in ice-water. When all the nitrile had been added, a clear brown solution was obtained, which was allowed to stand for 12 hours. The mixture was mixed with ethyl chloroacetate (65 g.) and after the initial reaction had abated, was boiled under reflux for about 15 hours. The filtered liquid was diluted with water, dried and the ether moved. The dicyano-ester distilled as a viscous liquid, b.p. 205-207°/4 mm., yield 60 g. (Found: C, 65.3; H, 5.7. C₁₇H₁₈O₄N₂ requires C, 65.0; H, 5.7 per cent).

*α -Phenyl-*n*-propane- $\alpha\beta\gamma$ -tricarboxylic Acid* (II, R = H).—The foregoing ester (40 c.c.) was mixed with sulphuric acid (70%, 240 c.c.) and boiled under reflux for 14 hours, the condenser being removed from time to time to allow the alcohol formed to escape. The cooled solution was then diluted with water extracted with ether and the ethereal extract treated

with sodium carbonate. The carbonate solution was acidified and extracted with ether. The acid obtained after removal of ether was heated on a water-bath with a solution of sodium hydroxide (15%) for 3-4 hours. The solution was extracted after acidification. The residue from ether was kept in a desiccator, when it solidified. It crystallised from water, m. p. 204°. (Found : C, 56.8; H, 4.5. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{12}O_6$: C, 57.1; H, 4.7 per cent).

The triethyl ester of the above was obtained in an almost quantitative yield from the acid (7 g.) absolute alcohol (30 c.c.), concentrated sulphuric acid (2 c.c.), 3 litres of vapourised alcohol (3-4 hours). After dilution with a large volume of water, the ester was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution was shaken with sodium bicarbonate solution and washed again, dried with sodium sulphate and ether removed. It was distilled at 185-190°/5 mm., yield 6 g. (Found : C, 64.0; H, 7.1. $C_{18}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 64.3; H, 7.1 per cent).

1-Keto-tetrahydronaphthalene-3 : 4-dicarboxylic Acid (III, R = CO).—The acid (II, R = H; 5 g.) was heated with sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84, 20 g.) on the water-bath for 2 hours. The product was poured into ice and after working up in the usual manner was crystallised several times from water, m. p. 179-82°, yield 1.5 g.. (Found : C, 61.4; H, 4.3. $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 61.5; H, 4.2 per cent).

Oxidation of 1-Ketotetrahydronaphthalene-3 : 4-dicarboxylic Acid.—The acid (4 g.) in sodium hydroxide solution, was heated on the steam-bath and oxidised with a warm saturated solution of potassium permanganate until the colour persisted. After destroying the excess of permanganate, the solution was filtered and the filtrate acidified and extracted with ether, the ethereal extract yielded phthalic acid, which after crystallisation from water was identified by mixed m.p.

1:2:3:4-Tetrahydronaphthalene-1:2-dicarboxylic Acid (III, R = CH_2).—The pure keto-acid (5 g.), amalgamated zinc (40 g.), and concentrated hydrochloric acid (40 c.c.) were refluxed for 12 hours, more acid (40 c.c.) was then added and the heating continued for 12 hours. The gummy product, obtained after working up in the usual manner, was kept in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid for a long time, when a small quantity of an acid crystallised out, m.p. 193° (rapid heating). (*cf.* Auwers and Moller, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1925, ii, 109, 124). (Found : C, 65.2; H, 5.4. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$: C, 65.4; H, 5.5 per cent).

*Diethyl $\alpha\beta$ -Dicyano- α -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-propane- $\beta\gamma$ -dicarboxylate* (I, R' = OMe; R = CH_2CO_2Et).—Anisaldehyde cyanohydrin (68 g.) was

gradually added to the alcoholic suspension of sodiocyanoacetate, prepared from ethyl cyanoacetate (56 g.), alcohol (140 c.c.) and sodium (11.6 g.). Considerable heat was generated after each addition and the temperature was regulated by cooling. The clear brown solution was allowed to stand for 12 hours and the mixture mixed with ethyl chloroacetate (70 g.) and after the initial reaction had abated, was boiled under reflux for about 15 hours. It was filtered and washed with dry ether, the filtrate diluted with water and extracted with ether; the ethereal solution was washed with water, dried and the ether removed. The dicyano-ester distilled as a viscous liquid, b.p. $232\text{--}37^\circ/3$ mm., yield 40 g. (Found: C, 63.1; H, 5.9; $C_{18}H_{20}O_5N_2$ requires C, 62.8; H, 5.8 per cent).

o-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-*n*-propane- $\alpha\beta\gamma$ -tricarboxylic Acid (II, R=OMe).—A solution of the above cyano-ester (20 g.) in concentrated sulphuric acid (22 c.c.) was diluted with water (320 c.c.) and refluxed for 50 hours on a sand-bath. After cooling, the mixture was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ether solution was dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent removed. It was crystallised from water, m.p. 190° (rapid heating), yield 8 g. (Found: C, 55.13; H, 4.8; Equiv., 95.0. $C_{13}H_{14}O_7$ requires C, 55.3; H, 4.9 per cent Equiv., 94.0).

The triethyl ester of the above acid was obtained in an almost quantitative yield by the alcohol vapour method from the acid (20 g.), absolute alcohol (100 c.c.), concentrated sulphuric acid (7 c.c.), 3 litres of vapourised alcohol (3.4 hours). After dilution with a large volume of water the ester was extracted with ether; the ether solution was shaken with sodium bicarbonate solution and washed again, dried with sodium sulphate and ether removed. It distilled at $210\text{--}15^\circ/5$ mm., yield 18 g. (Found: C, 62.6; H, 6.9. $C_{19}H_{26}O_7$ requires C, 62.29, H, 7.1 per cent).

Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -Dicyano- β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-*propionate* (I, R'=OMe; R=H). It was obtained by the condensation of anisaldehyde cyanohydrin (55 g.) with sodioethyl cyanoacetate as before. The clear solution obtained on keeping overnight was poured into water and the solution acidified with hydrochloric acid and the oil extracted with ether, the ethereal solution was washed several times with water to remove most of the alcohol, then thoroughly with a dilute solution of sodium carbonate and after drying over calcium chloride ether was evaporated. The dicyano ester distilled as a viscous liquid, b.p. $225^\circ/5$ mm., solidifying in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid. It crystallised from alcohol as colourless crystals, m.p. 81° , yield 30 g. (Found: N, 11.1. $C_{14}H_{14}O_5N_2$ requires N, 10.85 per cent).

p-Methoxyphenylsuccinic Acid.—A solution of the above cyano-ester (40 g.) in concentrated sulphuric acid (45 c.c.) was diluted with water (320 c.c.) and refluxed for 40 hours on a sand-bath. After cooling, the crystals separated which were filtered and crystallised from hot water, m.p. 205°. (Found: C, 59.3; H, 5.2. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{12}O_5$: C, 58.9; H, 5.4 per cent).

p-Methoxyphenylsuccinic Anhydride.—The above acid was boiled with acetyl chloride for 1 hour and after removing acetyl chloride in a vacuum desiccator over caustic potash, it was obtained as crystals, m.p. 91° (mixed m.p.).

Diethyl (*p*-methoxyphenyl)succinate was obtained by refluxing the acid (15 g.) with alcohol (100 c.c.) in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid (15 g.) for 5 hours. b.p. 185°/4 mm., yield 15 g. (Found: C, 64.6; H, 6.9. $C_{23}H_{26}O_5$ requires C, 64.3; H, 7.1 per cent).

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